

Validation of Sodium-Cooled Fast Reactor Assembly Calculations in the DRAGON5 Lattice Code

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ABSTRACT

Sodium-cooled fast reactor (SFR) assemblies impose demanding geometric and spectral requirements on lattice solvers. A validation workflow has therefore been established to qualify the DRAGON5 lattice code for the IRENA SFR assembly. The process begins with a 315-group library derived from ENDF/B-VIII.1 evaluations and Tone resonance self-shielding, which is benchmarked against OpenMC pin-cell calculations to confirm the fidelity of the multigroup collapse. Surface-element representations exported through the Geometric Lattice Optimization Workflow (GLOW) are then analysed with two complementary transport pathways: isotropic TISO tracking accelerated by the surface-element interface-current (IC) formulation and solved via collision probabilities, and Method of Characteristics tracking with specular reflection (TSPC) under the ARM iterative flux treatment. Each pathway is exercised under P_1 , and P_3 scattering expansions prior to comparison with OpenMC reactivity, reaction-rate, and pin-wise fission metrics. The resulting agreement demonstrates that the GLOW/DRAGON5 toolchain can reproduce Monte Carlo references for advanced SFR assemblies while delivering deterministic turnaround times suited for design optimisation.

Keywords: SFR, Deterministic methods, Lattice calculations, Reactor physics

1. INTRODUCTION

Sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFRs) remain a central element of the Generation IV roadmap because their hard spectrum enables sustainable closed fuel cycles and high breeding ratios while limiting long-lived radiotoxicity [1]. High-fidelity lattice physics is therefore essential both to produce reliable few-group data for core simulators and to guide design optimisation of emerging SFR concepts such as the IRENA assembly examined in the present work.

The IRENA core model is based on the ASTRID proposal in France [2]. The IRENA acronym stands for Incinérateur de résidus nucléo-atomiques, and the concept targets multi-recycling of plutonium together with minor actinide transmutation to preserve natural uranium resources while reducing nuclear waste. The industrial-scale 600 MW prototype was conceived with enhanced safety characteristics comparable to Generation III reactors, with the improved safety objective driving a core layout that delivers intrinsically safe behaviour when connected to the grid.

Deterministic analyses of these configurations have long been constrained by the geometric limits of DRAGON5's native macro-geometries. Modules such as NXT: and SALT: discretise clusters with canonical hexagonal or Cartesian surfaces, an approach that remains adequate for water-cooled lattices yet fails to capture the tight hexagonal pin map, stainless-steel wrapper, and inter-assembly sodium gap typical of fast-reactor subassemblies [3]. The Geometric Lattice Optimization Workflow (GLOW) [4] removes this restriction by exporting parametric or CAD descriptions to DRAGON5 as non-native "surface-element" geometries, thereby preserving the actual pin and duct layout while retaining compatibility with deterministic solvers.

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Energy treatment follows a parallel trajectory. Earlier DRAGON5 libraries focused on thermal systems and do not provide the fine-group resolution required by fast-spectrum nuclides. A dedicated 315-group SFR library has thus been generated from ENDF/B-VIII.1 evaluations using the standard DRAGON5 processing chain. This SHEM-315 mesh is derived from the SHEM-295 structure commonly used for LWR analysis by adding 16 energy groups above 1 keV and 4 groups in the epithermal range while retaining the same 34 thermal groups, thereby providing finer resolution in the fast-spectrum domain. Demonstrating the accuracy of this library against stochastic references is indispensable before extending the analysis to full assemblies.

This paper documents the first comprehensive validation of DRAGON5 for the IRENA SFR fuel assembly using the new geometric and nuclear-data capabilities. A staged workflow is implemented: the 315-group pin-cell reference models are benchmarked against OpenMC [5] to qualify the multigroup collapse prior to assembly calculations. The validated library is subsequently deployed on GLOW-generated surface-element models of the full assembly, where two complementary transport pathways are examined. Both pathways utilise Tone's method [6] for resonance self-shielding. The first activates isotropic tracking (TISO), i.e., non-cycling trajectories distributed uniformly under white boundary conditions, combined with the surface-element interface-current (IC) acceleration, in which each macro is solved by PIJ collision probabilities and adjacent macros are coupled through interface currents rather than a global $n_{\text{reg}} \times n_{\text{reg}}$ matrix. The second invokes specular tracking (TSPC), namely cyclic trajectories that replicate a convex lattice to infinity by specular reflections, rotations, or translations, in conjunction with the method of characteristics and the ARM iterative flux treatment. Both branches are exercised under P_1 , and P_3 scattering expansions so that the impact of angular order can be quantified. Comparison metrics include reactivity biases, reaction-rate ratios, and pin-wise fission rates, enabling a detailed assessment of deterministic accuracy. Section 2 outlines the modeling framework and transport options, Section 3 reports the numerical validation results, and Section 4 summarizes the main findings and recommendations for future SFR applications in DRAGON5.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. GLOW surface-element workflow

GLOW (Geometry Layout Oriented Workflow) is a Python package released by newcleo to support DRAGON5 users in building surfacic geometries directly from SALOME models.[4] The plug-in exploits SALOME's GEOM and GUI APIs and follows a model-view-controller architecture: geometry builder classes create the technological layout from OpenCASCADE primitives and boolean operations, while export classes recover the information required by any surfacic tracking solver (surface identifiers, orientation, macro/region incidence, boundary flags). Every action available through the graphical interface is mirrored by Python methods, so the same workflow can be executed interactively in the SALOME GUI or scripted for headless runs in batch mode. Metadata attached during export stores the intended tracking option (TISO or TSPC) so that SALT can assign the appropriate boundary condition.

Figure 1 captures the SALOME session used to cross-check the final layout. The Object Browser lists the hierarchical GEOM compounds (technological and sectorised layouts), the 3D viewer displays material-coloured regions, and the embedded Python console exposes the same API used by the batch scripts. Once validated, the exported deck is directly shared by both the TISO/IC and TSPC/MOC calculation chains described later in this section. The close coupling between Python automation and GUI inspection proved valuable when iterating on the IRENA assembly description.

Figure 1. GLOW plug-in within SALOME used to export surface-element geometry for four IRENA assemblies.

2.2. Surface-element interface-current (IC) method

The surface-element interface-current (IC) approach couples sub-geometries (“macros”) by defining interface currents on *surface elements*—i.e., short segments of each macro face—rather than on entire faces. In DRAGON5, this capability is enabled when SALT: reads a SURFIL file generated by G2S: or exported from SALOME via GLOW. The SURFIL file enumerates the macro partition, the set of surface elements belonging to each macro, and a connectivity table that matches neighbouring elements across macro boundaries [4, 7].

Within each macro, region-averaged scalar fluxes are computed with collision probabilities (PIJ). Macros are then coupled through their interface currents according to the SURFIL connectivity. In the implementation used here, currents on each surface element are treated *isotropically* (a DPO half-space description), and the global flux–current fixed-point iteration is terminated when the user-specified tolerance EPSJ is satisfied [7].

In this work, the geometry is constructed in SALOME/GLOW; the SURFIL file and element-to-element connectivity are produced with G2S:; and the IC branch uses SALT: with isotropic tracking (TISO) combined with collision probabilities. The alternative specular pathway (TSPC) is handled separately. Surface-element granularity is refined progressively and the impact is assessed against OpenMC. Macro boundaries are aligned with physical interfaces to promote stable convergence and to simplify the physical interpretation of inter-macro currents [7]. In practice, each macro is first solved independently by the PIJ solver, after which the flux–current iteration couples the set; a single macro covering the entire lattice therefore reduces to the NOIC behaviour, whereas a multi-macro partition activates a genuine interface-current treatment. For every macro, TISO tracks are generated and written sequentially to the track file, and SALT: automatically unfolds (splits) surfacic blocks when circular arcs intersect their perimeter, so that the IC formulation remains applicable [7].

2.3. Validation methodology

The validation sequence proceeds in two stages. First, the pin-cell problem is analysed with SALT: (TISO tracking), TONE:, and the 315-group library to qualify the multigroup collapse. Tone’s method has traditionally been applied to fast reactor analysis with fine or ultrafine group energy meshes [8]; it was recently adopted by Mao and Zmijarevic as an alternative to the subgroup approach for fast breeder reactor lattice analyses in APOLLO3 [9]. Compared with the USS: subgroup projection method, Tone’s method does not require Lebesgue integration techniques or Dancoff factor evaluations, making it CPU-efficient and numerically stable—properties particularly valued for computing Doppler reactivity coefficients [6]. The resulting k_{eff} , group fluxes, and EDI: reaction rates edits are compared with an OpenMC model based on the same geometry and temperatures; only after the pin-cell bias is deemed acceptable are assembly calculations undertaken.

Assembly-scale benchmarks reuse the identical microscopic data and geometry export. The specular pathway employs SALT: TSPC tracking and MCCGT:/ARM, scanning the scattering expansion via the ANIS parameter. The isotropic pathway activates the interface-current PIJ solve described above.

OpenMC reference tallies are post-processed into the same observables (reactivity, normalised pin-by-pin fission rates). Validation consists of reporting the DRAGON5–OpenMC reactivity differences and the residuals on normalised pin fission rates for each transport option and scattering order, allowing the impact of the library collapse and of the deterministic transport treatment to be assessed separately.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND VALIDATION

3.1. Pin-cell qualification

The pin-cell benchmark provides the first cross-check of the 315-group collapse. The reference cell corresponds to the IRENA MOX fuel rod with concentric regions representing the fuel pellet, the helium gap, the AIM1 cladding, and the surrounding liquid sodium coolant; temperatures of 750 °C (fuel), 620 °C (cladding), and 475 °C (sodium) are applied consistently in both DRAGON5 and OpenMC. The fuel pellet is subdivided into four concentric rings. Although distributed self-shielding effects within the fuel are less pronounced in fast spectra than in thermal lattices [6], the subdivision is retained to remain consistent with the assembly model and to verify that the spatial discretisation does not introduce bias at the pin-cell level. Table I shows that both the native DRAGON5 pin-cell model and the geometry exported through GLOW yield $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.4193$, corresponding to a bias of roughly -70 pcm with respect to the OpenMC reference ($k_{\text{eff}} = 1.4203$).

3.2. Assembly benchmarks

The assembly model is a 2D radial cross-section corresponding to one twelfth of the IRENA hexagonal subassembly. The fuel region contains 217 MOX pins surrounded by sodium, a perforated AIM1 wrapper, and the inter-assembly sodium gap, all described through the surface-element layout introduced in Sect. 2.2. The SURFIL header lists the perimeter segments (NB_PERIM) that connect macro domains and provides the counts of merged regions, surfaces, and nodes needed by the interface-current iteration.

Table I. Pin-cell k_{eff} comparison between DRAGON5 and OpenMC.

Code	k_{eff}	Δk (pcm)
DRAGON5 (native)	1.4193	-70.4
DRAGON5 (GLOW geometry)	1.4193	-70.4
OpenMC (reference)	1.4203	—

Table II. Assembly k_{eff} comparison (DRAGON5 vs. OpenMC).

Case	k_{eff}	Δk (pcm)
DRAGON5 TISO-IC	1.390563	+76.5
DRAGON5 TSPC (P_1)	1.390250	+54.0
DRAGON5 TSPC (P_3)	1.390184	+49.2
OpenMC reference	1.389500	—

Figure 2. GLOW/SALT macro partition for the one-twelfth IRENA sector. The SURFIL header lists NB_PERIM together with the merged-region, surface, and node counts used by the interface-current iteration.

The deterministic assembly models retain the MOX (Pu, U)O₂ fuel specification used for the pin-cell studies: each of the 271 fuel pins is divided into four concentric annuli at 750 °C, bounded by an internal helium cavity and an external helium gap at 620 °C. AIM1 steel cladding (also at 620 °C) reproduces the wire-wrap surrogate thickness, while liquid sodium at 475 °C fills the subchannels and inter-assembly gap. The hexagonal wrapper and duct employ EM10 steel maintained at the same sodium temperature to reflect the cooled structural environment.

The OpenMC reference mirrors this geometric description exactly, importing the same material zoning and temperatures as the deterministic deck. Simulations are performed with 10 inactive batches followed by 100 active batches, each containing 10 000 particles.

All three calculations keep the mean pin residual below 0.4% and the peak below 2% (Table III), with the largest deviations confined to the outer ring of pins adjacent to the inter-assembly sodium gap (Fig. 3). These observations complement the reactivity comparison in Table II.

Table III. Pin-wise relative difference metrics between DRAGON5 and OpenMC.

Case	mean $ \Delta $ (%)	max $ \Delta $ (%)
TISO-IC	0.316	1.578
TSPC P_1	0.352	1.753
TSPC P_3	0.387	1.875

DRAGON vs OpenMC pin power difference (TISO-IC)
 mean $|\Delta| = 0.32\%$, max $|\Delta| = 1.58\%$

(a) TISO-IC (mean $|\Delta| = 0.316\%$, max $|\Delta| = 1.578\%$)

DRAGON vs OpenMC pin power difference (TSPC-P1)
 mean $|\Delta| = 0.35\%$, max $|\Delta| = 1.75\%$

(b) TSPC P_1 (mean $|\Delta| = 0.352\%$, max $|\Delta| = 1.753\%$)

DRAGON vs OpenMC pin power difference (TSPC-P3)
 mean $|\Delta| = 0.39\%$, max $|\Delta| = 1.88\%$

(c) TSPC P_3 (mean $|\Delta| = 0.387\%$, max $|\Delta| = 1.875\%$)

Figure 3. Pin-wise DRAGON5/OpenMC relative differences for the deterministic transport options.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work assembled a complete SALOME–GLOW–DRAGON5 workflow for sodium-cooled fast reactor assembly analysis on the IRENA configuration. A dedicated 315-group fast-spectrum library with Tone resonance self-shielding was first qualified at the pin-cell level against OpenMC, showing a Δk of ~ 70 pcm (Table I). The same library and geometry description were then exercised on the full assembly via two complementary transport branches: (i) isotropic TISO tracking with the surface-element interface-current (IC) formulation and PIJ collision probabilities, and (ii) specular TSPC tracking with MCCGT and the ARM iterative flux treatment. Against OpenMC, assembly reactivity differences stayed within $\sim \mathcal{O}(10^2)$ pcm (Table II), while pin-wise fission-rate residuals averaged 0.316–0.387% with maxima below 2% and concentrated near the inter-assembly sodium gap (Figs. 3a–3c, Table III). Increasing the scattering expansion from P_1 to P_3 produced only modest reactivity changes, indicating that moderate angular order suffices for this case.

A central outcome of this study is the demonstrated value of GLOW as a solver-agnostic geometry layer that eliminates DRAGON5 native-geometry limitations for fast reactors. By constructing the true hexagonal pin map, stainless-steel wrapper, and inter-assembly sodium gap directly in SALOME and exporting a *surface-element* description, GLOW preserves geometric fidelity that is critical for SFR edge effects. The export carries surface identifiers, macro/region incidence, boundary flags, and tracking metadata (TISO/TSPC), and—together with the SURFIL connectivity generated by G2S:—enables the interface-current formulation to couple macros on refined surface elements.

Taken together, these results show that the GLOW/DRAGON5 toolchain reproduces Monte Carlo reference metrics for an advanced SFR assembly while offering deterministic turnaround well suited to design-space exploration and the generation of few-group data for core simulators. The combination of geometry fidelity from GLOW and complementary transport treatments in DRAGON5 provides a robust foundation for extending this validation to core-level homogenisation, physics perturbations (void and temperature coefficients), and multi-physics couplings in future work.

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